

THE ROLE OF MULTIMEDIA IN EDUCATION

Azamatov Rustam Alisherovich

Vice Principal at Presidential School in Gulistan,

alisherovich.090@gmail.com

Rajabov Khasan Ravshan Ugli

English teacher at Presidential School in Gulistan,

rajabovkhasan2@gmail.com

The contemporary world is experiencing rapid alterations, and the domain of education is significantly influenced by these transformations, especially in relation to Media Services. The paradigm of a self-contained audio-visual department in an academic institution is now a thing of the past. The proliferation of multimedia in the education landscape has witnessed a notable surge in the last few years, and this trend shows no signs of abating in the foreseeable future.

The application of multimedia in the context of education has been subject to extensive academic scrutiny, with compelling evidence supporting its effectiveness in enhancing productivity and retention rates amongst learners. According to Clark and Mayer (2016), empirical evidence indicates that individuals tend to retain 20%, 40%, and approximately 75% of visual, auditory, and multisensory information, respectively. The significance of this matter is particularly notable within the domain of Computer-Based Training (CBT) modules that are utilized in various organizations such as Ernst & Young and Union Pacific, where multimedia elements are incorporated to educate employees on organizational protocols. Similarly, flight simulations have become a critical aspect of pilot training within the aviation sector.

The integration of multimedia into the pedagogical framework has achieved pervasive prevalence due to its efficaciousness as a teaching and learning instrument. Multimedia facilitates the dissemination of information in a more compelling fashion, rendering it a remarkably efficacious medium for imparting instruction (Clark &

Mayer, 2016). The provision of a multi-sensory experience for the audience engenders favorable dispositions towards the application. Furthermore, studies indicate that multimedia is associated with superior information retention rates and expedited learning (Clark & Mayer, 2016).

The creation of interactive and multi-sensory multimedia applications presents creators with both difficulties and opportunities for growth. According to Clark and Mayer (2016), this provides novel perspectives on the process of learning, and demands that designers present information and knowledge in inventive manners.

The term multimedia pertains to the amalgamation of distinct forms of digital media, including text, images, sound, and video, which are skillfully combined into an interactive platform or presentation designed to evoke a multisensory response in the viewer and effectively communicate a particular message or relevant information. (Vaughan, 1998). This entails the engagement of individuals or small cohorts in the process of interaction with diverse media formats that facilitate their discretion in selecting the content they perceive and absorb.

The application of multimedia is redefining communication practices through enhancing the efficiency and comprehensibility of message delivery. The integration of media components serves to strengthen the conveyed message and bolster its efficacy in imparting knowledge, ultimately yielding superior learning outcomes. The effectiveness of multimedia lies in its capacity to engage multiple senses of the viewer, thereby stimulating an extensive range of sensory perceptions. Furthermore, the system exhibits interactivity, affording users the agency to regulate both the substance and dissemination of information, as posited by Vaughan (1998). The phenomenon of multimedia evolution has bestowed upon learners a greater sense of agency, allowing them to actively engage with their educational material. The employment of multimedia technologies enables students to develop multimedia applications as a mandatory element in their project assignments, thus transforming them into active participants in their own learning journey as opposed to being passive receivers of education.

Educators necessitate the availability of instructional materials that facilitate comprehension of concepts through various modalities so as to cater to the distinctive learning prerequisites of each student. The advent of multimedia technologies has facilitated novel prospects for instruction, both in educational institutions and domestic settings. The provision of multimedia learning resources that support constructive concept development is a means of empowering educators to act as learning facilitators as they attend to the needs of individual students. The integration of multimedia learning resources into the domestic environment presents a unique educational prospect that possesses the ability to amplify student learning efficacy (Vaughan, 1998).

The constituent components of multimedia have been in existence autonomously prior to their integration into the multimedia domain. The amalgamation of various media elements within a single platform, commonly referred to as multimedia, has emerged as a potent instrument, particularly in the domain of education. Incorporating five pivotal media genres, namely text, video, sound, graphics, and animation, interactive multimedia is interwoven into the educational milieu. The employment of interactive multimedia in the process of learning affords a non-linear and interactive educational experience, allowing both instructors and learners to determine their individualized routes of inquiry (Neo & Neo, 2000). In contrast to the conventional approach of sequential reading, interactive multimedia learning takes on the form of an intricate web, with interlinking concepts and options presented throughout the student's trajectory.

The educational domain has witnessed notable advancements in recent years, particularly in relation to multimedia technologies. Among the various multimedia technologies available, the ones that have evidently had substantive effects on education are those that complement the existing curriculum, and offer prompt and meaningful improvements, thus creating a favorable milieu for further curriculum development. The World Wide Web (WWW) functions as an extensive repository of information that learners can utilize in their search for subject matter content that aligns

with their individualized learning objectives. Multimedia applications designed for a range of computing platforms, including Personal Computers, Apple Macintosh, and gaming machines, have been developed (Neo & Neo, 2000).

Incorporating cutting-edge computer technologies to depict information and design computer-based learning resources may appear enticing; however, it is vital to devise the instructional foundation of these systems upon a thorough investigation and evaluation of various factors associated with visual learning. These factors encompass both human and technical aspects. It is crucial to give consideration to various inquiries, such as determining instances in which audio supersedes the significance of visual content, establishing a threshold for the acceptable amount of textual information, and ascertaining the point at which graphics inundate the viewer's display (Neo & Neo, 2000). The proposed method affords students the opportunity to integrate their learnt proficiencies from various disciplinary domains by deliberate selection of appropriate multimedia resources. Through judicious deployment of these resources within the educational setup, the approach engenders optimal learning outcomes.

In the domain of education, multimedia technology is utilized for the purpose of developing computer-based training courses (CBTs) as well as reference materials like encyclopedias and almanacs. Cognitive-behavioral therapies (CBTs) allow individuals to interact with a succession of displays, textual literature pertaining to particular subjects, and related illustrations in a range of formats as indicated by Vaughan (1998). The notion of "edutainment" is commonly employed in an informal manner to refer to the fusion of education and entertainment, predominantly within the domain of multimedia-based entertainment (Vaughan, 1998).

The erudite domain of learning theory has undergone significant augmentation over the past decade attributable to the incorporation of multimedia technologies, subsequently giving rise to the emergence of multifarious research streams, including cognizance overload and multimedia-based instruction (Mayer, 2009). The integration of multimedia in the arena of education has initiated a plethora of opportunities for

learning and pedagogy, thereby bringing about a significant transformation in the domain.

Media convergence, characterized by the amalgamation and interactivity of disparate technologies including voice, data, and video, has emerged as a vital aspect of higher education, transforming the educational curricula globally (Jenkins, 2006). The current confluence of technologies is resulting in newly formed efficiencies and is exerting an influence on the job market, underscoring the criticality of possessing technical proficiencies across a varied range of professions.

In the realm of English language education in middle schools within China, substantial investments and assistance have been extended for equipment and resources. Despite these efforts, however, the intended goal has yet to be accomplished, as noted by Yang and Sun (2013). There has been a prevalence of prioritizing the enhancement of numerical scores rather than the practical development of skills. In order to discontinue this recurring pattern, academicians are tasked with contemplating strategies to augment the education framework and ameliorate the inherent practical English proficiencies of learners. Multimedia teaching is capable of producing a dynamic educational setting, enabling students to engage actively with both their instructor and the subject being learned (Yang & Sun, 2013). The implementation of multimedia teaching enables a heightened level of intuitive and immersive educational engagement, thereby facilitating the simulation of real-life scenarios for pedagogical purposes. In numerous cases, educators have the capacity to withdraw from active involvement, enabling learners to engage in self-directed learning within the classroom setting. Moreover, multimedia instruction offers instructors various methods to elicit students' enthusiasm for education (Yang & Sun, 2013).

References

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